

Flavonoid Components of *Alleum cepa*

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A *ALLEUM CEPA* belongs to the family Liliacae. The bulb is useful in vomiting and diseases of spleen. The seeds are useful in caries of the teeth¹.

A review of the literature showed that the skins and other parts of white, yellow and dark red varieties of *Alleum cepa* have been reported to contain flavonoids²⁻¹⁸. Since no work has been reported on the flavonoid components from the light pink variety, the study of the flavonoid components of this variety was undertaken.

The skins of light pink variety of *Alleum cepa*, locally known as Malwi onion, were obtained from the local market and extracted with petroleum ether, which removed all the waxy and oily matter. The defatted skins were then extracted with methanol, the methanol extract concentrated and the dark brown mass obtained was successively extracted with petroleum ether and ether. The ether extract on concentration gave a dark brown mass, which on chromatography on Whatman filter paper No. 1 and on TLC showed the presence of two ferric positive spots. It was chromatographed on a column of silica gel and eluted with benzene and ethyl acetate: benzene [(i) 10:90; (ii) 20:80 and (iii) 50:50]. The elutes (i), (ii) and (iii) gave compound A, a mixture of compounds A & B and compound B respectively. The mixture was separated by repeated column chromatography.

The compound A (m.p. 272°-74°) was phenolic and on a TLC plate and on paper gave a yellow colour on exposure to ammonia vapours. The usual colour tests showed it to be flavonoid in nature and the

formation of orange red precipitate with lead acetate indicated it to be a flavonol. Negative Molisch test indicated the absence of glycosidic nature. It was identified as kaempferol by m.m.p. and superimposable I.R. spectra.

Similarly, compound B (m.p. 310°-12°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 197°-98°) was found to be quercetin.

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